

The Impact of Human Resource Cost on the Profitability of Firms: Empirical Evidence of Selected Listed Companies on Ghana Stock Exchange

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Abstract

the study's objective was to assess the impact of human resource cost thus staff cost on profitability of firms. The scope of the study was listed companies on Ghana Stock Exchange and it selected 42 listed companies as its sample for a period five years from 2014 to 2018. The study employed non-probability sampling technique thus convenient sampling to select the companies used due to availability of data. As the study used exploratory method, it used panel data methodologies to arrive at its conclusion. These methodologies used are unit root, cointegration test, correlation matrix, censored tobit regression method and robust least square regression method. In summary, the study found out that human resource cost thus staff cost negatively relate to profitability of companies in Ghana statistically. As the argument as to whether human resources of organizations should be considered as assets in order to value their productivity rather than being part of organizations expenditures which one way or the other affects their profitability.
Keywords: Human resource cost, Profitability, Ghana Stock Exchange, Censored tobit regression, Robust least square

1. Introduction

Success of company undertakings strictly depends upon the standard of human resources. It is accentuated that; Human resource is the most vital input in any company or enterprise. The investments directed to lift knowledge; skills and aptitudes of the workforce of the organization are the ultimate investments in human resource. In this context, it's worthy to look at the human resource cost practices of the corporate sector in Ghana and to grasp how human resource cost is affecting the financial and entire performance of the company. It is merely a trial to characteristic measurement and human activity information concerning human resources and it needs to be viewed as an image. It's the approach of containing the management of individuals. It is a recording of transactions associated with the worth of human resources. A popular development among the business world is to disclose information with reference to human resource in yearly financial statements. In this regard, it's necessary to conduct a study to assess the revealing pattern of human resource cost information of some Ghanaian companies.

According to Syed (2009), Human Resource may be a term that refers to the set of people who comprises of the personnel of a company or a business entity. Moreover, it encompasses the energies, skills and information of individuals that are or that doubtless will be applied to the assembly of products or rendering helpful services. The success of any organization thrives on the power of its human resources to effectively and expeditiously optimize alternative resources like land, financial earnings and equipment thus human resources are the best assets at the disposal of companies. This can be why the statement "our greatest assets are our people" is said in most companies' annual reports (Enofe et al., 2013). The work of Bassey and Tapang (2012) points to the actual fact that human resources are known mutually of the most sources of competitive advantage by several organizations in today's economy. Significantly, the private sector firms or organizations are widely numerous and has centred on human resources as having special strategic price for organization development.

Abdullahi and Kirfi (2012) maintain that the quantification of the worth of Human Resources helps the management to cope up with the changes in its quantum and quality so equilibrium will be achieved within specified resources and therefore the provided human resources. As a result, it becomes imperative to place measures in situ to effectively manage individuals with their wants and expectations to boost productivity. Therefore, correct appreciation of human resource cost can modify managers take acceptable selections relating to investment in human resources. It will additionally offer information relating to prices

comparatively benefits and costs related to investments in human assets. It's a true statement that information in relation to human quality has not been noticeable and conferred on the plan of organizations and it makes it tough to live or value the important profit of a firm. The growing trend towards the activity and coverage of human resource quality in company annual reports is especially not noticeable within the financial report of company or organizations by charging expenses of accomplishment, training, familiarization and development of human resources to this period's profit or loss account, minimize profits or mislead losses, by not cost for expenses associated with human resources, even when they conceal their substantial net worth and assets.

Human Resource Cost information are often helpful for decision making in managerial context in numerous areas; several studies have been conducted to prove this. Tomassini (1977) meted out a laboratory study to examine the results of HUMAN RESOURCE COST information in personnel cost estimates to close down on personnel downsizing context. He inferred that human resource cost estimates caused totally different preferences in decision making within the personnel lay off context. Gul (1984) attempted to check the utility of human resources turnover cost information for labour turnover decision making in a sample of Australian Cost companies. Thomas Bayes (1984) conducted associate empirical investigation of the effects of human resource cost info on decision-making. Malik (1993) meted out associate empirical investigation to grasp the impact of human resource cost information on decision making. Sen et.al (2008) in their study build a scientific investigation into whether or not human resource info has any impact on internal decision-making i.e. within the context of personnel management decision-making associated with worker accomplishment and ratio management in banking industry of East Pakistan. There are such a numerous of studies that support the hypothesized utility of human resource cost in the process of decision by internal and external users. There has additionally been associate increasing recognition of the conception of human resource cost, proved by the flow of literature on varied aspects of human resource cost. However, there are only a few organizations concerned within the systematic activity and coverage of human resource cost info. Although the users of the information have an interest and that they welcome human resource cost coverage, however they fail to throw light-weight on this vacuum created by the resistance of the organizations to adopt a system of human resource cost. It is very important to grasp the perceptions of the management concerning the precise uses to that human resource cost information are often put. As a result of its management, to come to a decision concerning adoption of system of human resource cost and in what type it ought to be made offered to the internal and external users.

Even though, many studies have been done by some scholars and authors on basis on human resource cost and this idea can be traced by back to many years ago, the concept's acceptability has not widely been endorsed. There are major confrontations with regards to human resources cost as many organisations do not report the concept in their financial statements. This study intends to find out whether human resource costs does significantly affect profitability be the reason why most companies do not report cost of human resources as assets in their financial statement. The scope of the study stems from the Ghana Stock Exchange as the study relies on forty-two (42) selected listed companies to ascertain the impact of human resource or capital cost on their profitability. The study aims to apply econometric model to analysis its data to make strong statistical inference and contribute to existing literatures on the subject-matter.

The study is organised into five sections; section 1 introduces the study, section 2 presents the theoretical background of the study and some literature review, section 3 explains the study's data and methodology, section 4 presents the results and findings discussion and the last section thus section 5 concludes the study.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Background

- Human Capital Theory

Human capital is referred to the productive capabilities of individuals in economic literatures (Becker, 1964). Skills, knowledge and experience to organizations have economic value as a result of their ability to be productive and adaptable; therefore, individuals represent the organization's human capital. Like different assets, human capital has worth within the market place, however in contrast to different assets the potential worth of human capital is absolutely complete solely with the cooperation of the person. Therefore, all

associated costs with eliciting productive behaviours from workers together with those associated with motivating, retaining, and monitoring. Katz and Kahn (1978), outlined role behaviours as "the continual action of a personal, fittingly reticulated with the repetitive activities of others therefore yield an inevitable outcome." Human resource management is that the organization's primary way for delivery information through the organization, supporting desired behaviours and evaluating role performances; it's effective, therefore, once it communicates internally consistent expectations and evaluates performances in ways in which are congruent with the system's behavioural needs (Frederickson, 1986). System needs are, in turn, probable to rely on discourse factors like business methods and also the nature of the business. Role theory acknowledges that the behavioural expectations of all role partners will influence the behaviour of structure members. By implication, effective HRM helps workers meet the expectations of role partners inside the organization (i.e. supervisors, peers subordinates), at structure boundaries (i.e. customers and clients), and on the far side (i.e. family and society). Therefore, the expectations of those role partners should be incorporated into an understanding of human resource management in context then represent human capital investments created in anticipation of future returns.

- Resource Based View Theory

The resource-based view theory of the organizations blends ideas from structure strategic management and organizational economics (Barney, 1991). A fundamental assumption of this theory is that organizations will be booming if they gain and maintain competitive advantage (Porter, 1985). Competitive advantage is gained by implementing a value-creating strategy that competitors cannot, simply copy and sustain (Barney, 1991) and that there are not any prepared substitutes. For competitive advantage to be gained, 2 conditions are required. First, the resources accessible to competing organizations should be variable among competitors, and second, these resources should be immobile (i.e. not simply obtained). There are forms of resources related to organizations thus:

i. Physical (plant; technology and equipment; geographical location)

ii. Human (employees' expertise and knowledge); and structure (structure; systems for designing, monitoring, and dominant activities; social relations at intervals the organization and between the organization and external constituencies)

Human resource management greatly influences an organization's human and structure resources that enable them to gain competitive advantage (Schuler & Macmillan, 1984). Presumably, the extent to that human resource management could be used to gain competitive advantage, and also the means that of doing therefore, are determined by the environments within which organizations operate. For instance, in some industries, technologies will substitute for human resources, whereas in others the human part is prime to the business parenthetically distinction knowledge intensive and labour-intensive industries. The latter context is also a lot of contribute immensely to the employment of human resource management as a way to realize competitive advantage.

On the tenet of these two theories, the study draws its motivation to empirically assess the impact of human resources cost on profitability of companies to find out whether the assertions of these theories exist in the samples considered for the study.

2.2 Empirical literature review

Accountants haven't invariably been in complete agreement on the summary which means of the language used. So, a quick review of the literature is critical to find what criteria are relevant to be considered in the context of an asset. Human resource has been thought of as an indoor element of goodwill worth as way back as 1932. Historically, the practice of cost has recognized the goodwill worth within the accounts of the surviving entity in every business combination on the premise that the assets of the "purchased" entity ought to be recorded at their truthful or market value fairly. The excess of the value of purchased or acquired company over the sum of net assets identifiable is typically referred to as goodwill (AICPA, 1970). Cost profession has prerequisite that the value of every form of intangible assets ought to be

amortized by systematic charges to financial gain over the amount calculable to be benefited (AICPA, 1970).

According to Newman (1999), human resource cost refers to the activity of the talents of all workers of an organization, at each level management, higher-up and standard workers to provide worth from their data and therefore the capabilities of their minds. This definition considers the present growth within the industry wherever the data and intellectual capabilities of workers square measure the key for fulfilment. As such, human resource cost is seen because the wealth of the employees' knowledge and intellectual capabilities are added to cushion the organization thereby enabling it to earn profit and in order to succeed. Looking at the trend of definitions within the field of human resource cost, as highlighted previously, the study then defines human resource cost as the measuring method that acknowledges value and cost of staff within the financial statements of a corporation, as intangible, so exact cost of the organization is established thereby helping the varied users of the financial statements in support of decision making by stakeholders.

According to Obara (2013), the most important objective of human resource cost is to clarify the gap between the market and therefore the value of an enterprise. In doing this, the contribution of an important issue (personnel) is evaluated. Gebauer (2003), stressed that the procedures are classified on the premise of two distinctive features. First, the analysis objects and, second the scale of the result. As regards the analysis object, some ways target the analysis of individuals; different ways are aligned to perceptive the analysis by means that of teams. The second delicacy that's the scale of the result, deals with the determination of financial and non-monetary values for human capital. The non-monetary ways are directed at the determination of proportion numbers or at variety on a specifically crated scale. The financial ways on the opposite hand is differentiated in price and value-based ways (Sackman, 1989).

Profitability means the ability to gain benefit from all the business activities of a company, organization, firm, or an enterprise. It shows however expeditiously the management will create profit by exploitation of all the resources accessible within the market. With reference to Harward and Upton (2012), profitability of an entity is that 'the ability of a given investment to yield returns from its use. However, the term 'Profitability' isn't similar to the term 'Efficiency'. "Profitability is an index of efficiency"; and is considered a live of potency and management guide to larger efficiency. Though, profitability is a vital yardstick for quantifying the efficiency, the extent of profitability can't be considered as the major or final proof of efficiency. Typically, satisfactory profits will mark unskillfulness and conversely, a correct degree of efficiency may be in the midst of absence of profit. Net profit figure merely reveals a satisfactory balance between the received value and given value. The modification in operational efficiency is simply one in the various factors that profitability of an enterprise mostly depends on. Moreover, there are several alternative factors besides efficiency that have an effect on profitability.

3. Data and Methodology

3.1 Data

The study's data was collected from financial reports of forty-two (42) selected listed companies on the Ghana Stock Exchange for a period of five years spanning from 2014 to 2018. The study's independent variable is total staff cost and the dependent variable is retained profit. However, other variables were considered to control the relationship that exist between human resource cost (staff cost) and profitability. These variables are firm size, firm age, firm reputation and leverage. More details can be found in the table below.

Table 1 Variables description

VARIABLES	SYMBOLS	DEFINITION OR DETAILS
Profitability	PROFIT-ROA	Net income divided by total assets
Firm's Size	FIRM_SIZE	The size of the firm is calculated as, natural logarithm of non-current assets
Firm's reputation	FIRM_REP	Natural logarithm of the total number of the firm's customer base
Firm's age	FIRM_AGE	Firm's age at year t-1, is measured as the natural logarithm of one plus the number of years since firm 'j' obtained listing status.

Leverage	LEV_FIRM	Long term debt/long term assets
Human Capital Cost (Staff cost)	STAFFCOST	Total cost of staffing thus training and development, compensation and benefits

3.2 Methodology

The study adopted an exploratory research methodology and a panel study. As the data for the study was collected from forty-two selected companies on the Ghana Stock Exchange. The sampling technique used was a non-probability sampling as it is the method that enables a research by selecting samples from a population that the study has much interest in. Non-probability sampling technique is usually based on the subjective judgement of the study in question rather than random selection. Moreover, a convenient sampling technique was employed. The study is panel study hence the use of panel data methodologies such as panel unit root tests, cointegration test, correlation matrix, robust least square regression and censored tobit regression methods.

In order to achieve the objective of the study, the study constructed an econometric model for its regression analysis and this model is specified as;

Profitability = f (staff cost, firm’s age, firms’ size, firm’s reputation, leverage) hence the equation below;

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + (\beta_1 X_1)_{it} + (\beta_2 X_2)_{it} + \dots + (\beta_n X_n)_{it} + \mu$$

In the equation, Y refers to Profitability thus the dependent variable, β_0 represents the constant term and coefficient of the intercept, $\beta_1 X_1$ to $\beta_n X_n$ represent the independent variables thus staff cost, firms’ age, firms’ size, firms’ reputation, leverage and their coefficients whilst μ represents the stochastic error term or the disturbance in the model. Moreover, i represents the cross section of the 42 companies or panel sampled for the study and t represents the time period from 2014 to 2018.

The first step of the study is to compute the descriptive statistics of the variables to ascertain the order of data distribution and also identify the mean, median, standard deviation and skewness. Subsequently, unit root test is performed to ascertain whether the variables are stationary hence no problem of unit to reject the null hypothesis that there is unit root in the variables hence further performance of the regression analysis makes it spurious. Afterwards, the study further checks for multicollinearity with the aid of correlation matrix. After it is evidenced that there is no problem of multicollinearity then it becomes necessary to move on to another test. Eventually, cointegration test follows suit and at this juncture, Kao cointegration test is performed to check for the long run relationship among the variables.

The final step is to run the regression analysis and at this stage, two regression methods have been considered thus censored tobit regression and robust least square regression methods. The robust least square regression method is used to robust check the main regression method thus censored tobit regression method.

4. Results and findings discussion

4.1 Descriptive statistics of the variables

Table 2 displays the summary or descriptive statistics of the variables and it reports the mean, median, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values of the variables as well as the skewness, Jarque-Bera and Kurtosis nature of the variable to ascertain the distribution of the data. However, the Jarque-Bera test confirms that only one variable is in normal distribution out of the six variables affirm that the data is not in normal distribution since majority of the variables showed p-values less 5%. Again, the distribution was both negatively and positively skewed which harnesses the adoption of non-parametric method for the study’s regression analysis. To account for the mean of the variables, it can be reported that average profitability of the sample companies stood at 35.8% annually within the sample years. Staff cost also grew at 106.8% annually whilst their leverage thus long-term debt as a ratio of long-term assets grew averagely at 68.4% annually. In addition, the firms’ size which is referred to as the natural logarithm of non-current

assets grew at an annual average rate of 559.5%, their reputation as in the number of customers or clients also grew at an annual average rate of 209.7%. More details can be found in table 2.

Table 2 Descriptive statistics of variables

	Profit	Staff Cost	Lev Firm	Firm Size	Firm Rep	Firm Age
Mean	0.358	1.068	0.684	5.595	2.097	1.022
Median	0.092	0.730	0.177	6.213	2.265	1.150
Maximum	7.236	15.024	10.795	8.612	4.490	1.430
Minimum	0.000	0.000	0.000	-8.012	0.000	0.000
Std. Dev.	0.946	1.688	1.374	2.508	1.030	0.423
Skewness	5.409	6.377	4.153	-2.811	-0.248	-1.448
Kurtosis	35.895	49.744	24.847	13.815	3.032	4.032
Jarque-Bera	10392.190	20346.420	4734.486	1287.599	2.139	81.923
Probability	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.343	0.000
Observations	208	208	208	208	208	208

4.2 Unit root tests

Unit root test is very essential in empirical studies hence it is imperative to perform such statistical requirement. Perhaps, it reveals the stationary features of variables to be used for regression analysis. Moreover, a null hypothesis exists and it posits that all variables have unit root hence eschewing such test to further perform regression analysis makes the results spurious. Therefore, the study employed the proposed tests from Levin, Lin and Chu, Im Persaran and Shin and ADF and PP Fisher Chi-square tests. Evidence from these tests can be found in table 3. Firstly, the tests were performed at level form and the results showed that all variables showed stationarity status except firms’ reputation (Firm_rep) and firms’ age (Firm_age) which only passed on test thus Levin, Lin and Chu test. Subsequently, the tests were performed at first difference and at the level, all the variable became stationary hence the null hypothesis was rejected at 1% and 5% significance level respectively.

Table 3 Panel unit root tests

Level Form	Staff cost	Profit	Firm size	Firm_rep	Firm_age	Lev_firm
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-78.035***	-12.554***	-260.974***	-28.420***	-1.711**	-28.196***
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-10.217***	-3.771***	-67.240***	-1.156	-1.063	-4.791***
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	112.537**	95.535**	150.958***	43.527	67.248	113.158**
PP - Fisher Chi-square	138.305***	114.141***	185.413***	54.470	119.792***	135.201***
First Difference						
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-41.178***	-58.059***	-165.110***	-24.895***	-18.277***	-34.3769***
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	149.219***	150.692***	196.949***	78.079***	61.563**	125.174***
PP - Fisher Chi-square	160.810***	170.568***	219.634***	85.119***	76.402***	154.002***

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level

4.3 Correlation matrix

The computation of correlation matrix is necessary due to the fact that it enables the study to fish out the correlation between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Moreover, it also helps to identify and check for collinearity and multicollinearity. The rule of thumb for collinearity postulates that no independent variable should have a higher coefficient value of $-/+0.70$ or above with the dependent variable else it will result in collinearity. Also no one or more variables should have the same coefficient values with the dependent variable else the problem of multicollinearity will ensue. Table 4 exhibits the correlation matrix for the study and from the table, it can report that the independent variable thus staff cost has positive

and insignificant correlation with profitability thus profit with coefficient value of -0.079 as well as firms' size and leverage with values of -0.056 and -0.003 respectively. On the other hand, firms' reputation and firms' age have positive and significant correlation with profitability at 10% and 5% significance level respectively.

Table 4 Correlation Matrix

Correlation	Profit	Staff Cost	Lev Firm	Firm Size	Firm_Rep	Firm Age
PROFIT	1					
STAFFCOST	-0.079	1				
LEV_FRM	-0.003	-0.024	1			
FIRM_SIZE	-0.056	0.168**	0.039	1		
FIRM_REP	0.125*	0.224***	-0.038	0.328***	1	
FIRM_AGE	0.192**	0.166**	-0.011	0.243***	0.727***	1

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level, * indicates 10% significance level

4.4 Cointegration test

In order to establish the fact that the study's variables are cointegrated hence there is a long run relationship between the variables, cointegration test then becomes necessary to unravel such assumption. Apparently, Kao cointegration was used in that regard and perhaps the results in table 5 report orderly. The results show that the variables are cointegrated hence the null hypothesis that posits that there is no long run relationship among the variables is rejected at 1% significance level.

Table 5 Panel cointegration test

Kao Residual Cointegration Test Null Hypothesis: No cointegration			
	t-Statistic	Prob.	Significance
ADF	-7.088595	0.000	***

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level

4.5 Regression analysis

4.5.1 Regression analysis with Censored Tobit method (Main Method)

The objective of the study is to assess the impact of human resource cost (staff cost) on the profitability of firms. In that regard, the study employed censored tobit regression as its main regression method to analysis the data sourced to make statistical conclusion. Table 6 reports that analysis performed with censored tobit regression method and from the outcome, it can report that human resource cost (staff cost) showed negative and statistically significant relationship with profitability in the long run with coefficient of -0.383 at 5% significance level. The result is consistent with literature of Obara (2013) and also affirms the resource-based view theory and human capital theory as these theories posit that human resource of organisation should be given market value in order to assess their productivity level and contribution to the profitability of firms. Human resource cost has in so many years become the bane of many enterprises and companies as it takes majority of firms' profit or income. The result displays in the study's regression analysis highlights the school of thought that human resource expenditure should be considered as assets rather than liabilities due to the toll it has on the profitability of firms. However, firms' age showed positive and statistically significant relationship with profit with coefficient of 1.206 at 1% significance level. This result implies that the older a firm, the higher its profitability as an old adage asserts that "the older you

become, the more experience you gain”. Moreover, the other variables showed coefficients of -0.077, -0.002 and 0.069 but the results were not significant to infer on.

Table 6 Regression analysis with censored tobit method

Dependent Variable: PROFIT					
Method: ML - Censored Normal (TOBIT)					
Sample: 2014 2018					
Included observations: 208					
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.	sig.
Staff cost	-0.383	0.131	-2.930	0.003	**
Firm Age	1.206	0.307	3.921	0.000	***
Firm_Rep	-0.077	0.127	-0.603	0.547	
Firm Size	-0.002	0.036	-0.049	0.961	
Lev_Firm	0.069	0.058	1.203	0.229	
Constant	-0.692	0.319	-2.167	0.030	**
Error Distribution					
SCALE:C(7)	1.119	0.067	16.818	0.000	***
Mean dependent var	0.358	S.D. dependent var		0.946	
S.E. of regression	0.943	Akaike info criterion		2.572	
Sum squared resid	178.868	Schwarz criterion		2.684	
Log likelihood	-260.460	Hannan-Quinn criter.		2.617	
Avg. log likelihood	-1.252				
Left censored obs	61	Right censored obs		0	
Uncensored obs	147	Total obs		208	

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level,

4.5.2 Robust check (Robust least square method)

Furthermore, the study intended to robust check the results produced by the censored tobit regression method in order to make strong statistical inference. However, it relied on robust least square method to do the robust check test. Nonetheless, the results produced by robust least square showed similar results as to the censored tobit regression method. Table 7 shows the results of the robust check regression analysis with robust least square and it can be reported that with coefficient of -0.017 at 5% significance level, staff cost thus human resource cost has negative and statistically significant relationship with profitability. Moreover, firms’ age showed positive and statistically significant relationship with profitability with coefficient of 0.133 at 5% significance level. Meanwhile, firms’ reputation, leverage and firms’ size all showed insignificant coefficients.

In account of the good to fitness of the regression method used to robust check the main regression method, the R² and the adjusted R² proved that method is fit for inference as it explained 54.5% variation of the independent variable on the dependent variable. However, the Rn-squared statistics showed 5% significance with statistics value of 17.104.

Table 7 Robust check method (Robust least square)

Dependent Variable: PROFIT					
Method: Robust Least Squares					
Included observations: 208					
Method: M-estimation					
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.	Sig.
Staffcost	-0.017	0.007	-2.464	0.014	**
Firm_Age	0.113	0.039	2.884	0.004	**
Firm_Rep	-0.017	0.017	-0.988	0.323	
Firm_Size	0.004	0.005	0.903	0.366	
Lev_Frm	-0.007	0.008	-0.873	0.383	
Constant	0.035	0.036	0.967	0.334	
Robust Statistics					
R-squared	0.545	Adjusted R-squared		0.522	

Rw-squared	0.512	Adjust Rw-squared	0.512
Akaike info criterion	331.850	Schwarz criterion	355.558
Deviance	7.613	Scale	0.153
Rn-squared statistic	17.104	Prob(Rn ² stat.)	0.004 **
Non-robust Statistics			
Mean dependent var	0.358	S.D. dependent var	0.946
S.E. of regression	0.981	Sum squared resid	194.444

Note: ** indicates 5% significance level

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the study's objective was to assess the impact of human resource cost thus staff cost on profitability of firms. The scope of the study was listed companies on Ghana Stock Exchange and it selected 42 listed companies as its sample for a period five years from 2014 to 2018. The study employed non-probability sampling technique thus convenient sampling to select the companies used due to availability of data. As the study used exploratory method, it used panel data methodologies to arrive at its conclusion. These methodologies are unit root, cointegration test, correlation matrix, censored tobit regression method and robust least square regression method.

In summary, the study found out that human resource cost thus staff cost negatively relate to profitability of companies in Ghana statistically. As the argument as to whether human resources of organizations should be considered as assets in order value their productivity rather than being part of organizations expenditures which one way or the other affects their profitability. The results from the study's regression analysis also imply that training cost, remuneration and development cost all negatively affect the performance of the companies. On the other, with reference to the study's model, firms' age contributes immensely in a positive manner to the profitability of organisations in a situation where both firms' size and staff cost exists.

Based on the findings, the study proposes these recommendations;

- 1) Organisations ought to ensure and harness the education of retention, development and training of their employees in the manner that could positively translate into economic gains rather than wastage of knowledgeable investment.
- 2) There should be the institution of cost standard for disclosure and valuation of human resource cost by accounting standard board.
- 3) Legal framework on company law should be incorporated in the context of disclosure of information on the value of human resources and their performance as part of their reporting during their cost years as part of notes and schedule.
- 4) The study recommends further studies into the area of human resource cost to position the necessity to value human resource costs as assets rather than expenditure.

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